

Objectives and strategic plans for VKM 2008-2011

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About the Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food Safety (VKM)

The food safety structure in Norway is similar to the system practiced Europe-wide, and has since 2004 been based on the principles of risk analysis that led to the establishment of the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA). VKM was established in 2004 to fill the need for scientific, independent and transparent risk assessments within the food chain.

In Norway risk management is the responsibility of the Norwegian Food Safety Authority (Mattilsynet). VKM carries out independent risk assessments on request from Mattilsynet throughout their field of responsibility. Since April 2007, VKM is also responsible for environmental risk assessments of GMOs for the Directorate for Nature Management (DN). VKM only accepts requests from Mattilsynet and DN. If other government bodies, institutions, or organisations require risk assessments to be conducted by VKM, these must be raised via Mattilsynet or DN. The Committee can also undertake risk assessments on its own initiative, thereby ensuring that topics considered important and relevant are scientifically assessed, regardless of whether they are on the agenda of other government agencies.

The risk assessments from VKM are used by Mattilsynet and DN as basis for their risk management measures and priorities, and are also used as scientific background by the ministries in their establishment of appropriate levels of protection. VKM is consequently an important participant in ensuring safe food, feed and cosmetics, high standards in animal health and animal welfare, good plant health, and that relevant environmental hazards are taken into account.

VKM consists of a Scientific Steering Committee and 9 scientific panels, comprising a total of 90 members, who are appointed by the Ministry of Health and Care Services for a three-year period. Most of the members are employed by scientific institutions throughout Norway. They are appointed to VKM on their own merits, not as representatives of their employers.

VKM has its own secretariat, with a staff of fourteen persons, responsible for assisting the Committee, in scientific and administrative matters. The Secretariat ensures that important documents are available to anyone who is interested. Such documents include:

- Calls for application for membership of the Committee.
- Lists of appointed members, including their places of work and scientific backgrounds.
- Agendas and minutes from meetings in the Scientific Steering Committee, the Scientific Panels, and special working groups.
- Lists of finalized risk assessments and assessments currently being carried out.
- All completed risk assessments in full text.

The information is primarily available through the web pages at www.vkm.no.

There is broad international cooperation in the field of food safety. International standards, guidelines, and definitions from relevant organisations (EFSA, Codex, IPPC, EPPO, OIE a.o.) are applied in the work of VKM. Many risk assessments from VKM are published in English.

VKM vision

VKM shall be the cornerstone in the work for food safety in Norway

Objectives and strategic plans for the VKM Committee 2008-2011

Main objective 1

VKM shall provide an independent scientific basis for risk management

Part objectives:

- All the Committee's risk assessments shall be of high scientific quality and in accordance with international principles and standards
- The Committee will initiate scientific risk assessments in areas where it identifies a need for self-tasking
- The Committee shall identify gaps in knowledge and needs for research within the remit of VKM
- The Committee shall contribute to the development of expertise and knowledge within its remit

To achieve the part objectives VKM has chosen the following strategies:

- The Committee members will be given the opportunity to make active use of their special expertise in the risk assessment work
- VKM's panel chairs will secure that additional expertise is provided when the Committee lacks the required qualifications in the work with specific risk assessments
- The Committee will point out the need for research and lack of knowledge where relevant
- The Committee will contribute to the development of a quality assurance system for their risk assessments
- The Committee will, through the Secretariat, maintain a good dialogue with NFSA and DN throughout the process from request to finalized opinion

Main objective 2

VKM shall contribute to development and use of knowledge in order to ensure the quality of scientific risk assessments

Part objectives:

- The Committee shall have a good understanding of its role in risk analysis and of internationally recognised definitions, methods and principles
- The Committee shall apply the most up to date knowledge in its risk assessment work
- The Committee shall contribute to the further development of risk assessment methods
- The Members shall be updated on knowledge about risk assessments within their areas of expertise

To achieve the part objectives VKM has chosen the following strategies:

- The members will be given the opportunity, as far as possible, to participate at relevant seminars/conferences where the development of risk assessment is a topic
- The members will be given the opportunity to follow the development of risk assessment methods within in their areas of expertise
- VKM will strengthen co-operation with relevant institutions of expertise

Main objective 3

VKM will ensure transparency regarding its working procedures, easy access to its risk assessments and clear communication of the results

Part objectives:

- All risk assessments shall be comprehensible and easily accessible
- Information about risk assessments under development shall be easily available
- VKM's members shall contribute in communication of the results of the risk assessments
- The members shall contribute to increasing the visibility of VKM

To achieve the part objectives VKM has chosen the following strategies:

- The members will contribute to the preparation of short-versions of risk assessments with consumers, media and other stakeholders without expert knowledge as the main target group
- Panel chairs¹ will give statements to the media and other interested parties about finalized, published risk assessments
- The members will contribute with presentations of the risk assessments
- VKM will implement and apply the principles for transparency and openness developed by EFSA
- VKM will assist in explaining possible misunderstandings which may arise in connection with the risk assessments

¹ Or the person appointed by panel chair as responsible for communication about the particular risk assessment

Objectives and strategic plans for the VKM Secretariat 2008-2011

Tasks of the VKM secretariat

The Secretariat for VKM was established to help the Committee in scientific and practical matters. This includes coordinating the work in the Scientific Steering Committee, the Scientific Panels and, if required, between the panels. Development of good collaboration routines and a clear distribution of responsibilities between the Committee and the Secretariat are key words.

Furthermore, the Secretariat is responsible for a good and effective dialogue (risk communication) between the Norwegian Food Safety Authority (NFSA)/the Directorate for nature management (DN) and the Committee, and for publishing of the risk assessments. Transparent and accessible information about the work is one of the important tasks of the secretariat.

The Secretariat is also responsible for the general administration of VKM. This includes management tasks such as making annual work plans, budget planning and follow-up, contracts in connection with out-sourcing of preparatory work for the risk assessments, payment of allowances for meetings, practical and scientific preparations for meetings, organizing contact meetings with stakeholders and reporting to the Ministry of Health and Care Services (HOD).

The Director for the Secretariat is the Norwegian representative in EFSA's Advisory Forum. The Coordinator of the Scientific Steering Committee is functioning as Norwegian Focal Point for the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA).

Key objective for the Secretariat

An effective and well functioning VKM

To help the Committee achieve its goals the Secretariat has chosen the following strategies:

Scientific strategies

1. The Secretariat will be updated on the international development and ensure that VKM's risk assessments are in agreement with international standards
2. The Secretariat will ensure that published risk assessments are of high quality, both technically and scientifically
3. The Secretariat will make sure that the requests from NFSA/DN are clear and unambiguous and that the risk assessments from VKM give answers to the questions posed
4. The Secretariat will be National Focal Point for EFSA
5. The Secretariat will ensure good cooperation with NFSA/DN, the ministries with responsibility for the food chain, the Ministry of environment (MD) and national competence institutions.
6. The Secretariat will arrange seminars with different stakeholders and other interested parties (consumers, branch organisations, NFSA, ministries and others)
7. The Secretariat will give presentations about risk assessment at relevant, external forums

Administrative strategies

1. The Secretariat will provide for an effective and adequate administration of the Scientific Panels and the Scientific Steering Committee
2. The Secretariat will further develop routines for preparation and finalising of risk assessments in VKM and make sure that they are followed
3. The Secretariat will develop a communication strategy for VKM
4. The Secretariat will ensure transparency and accessibility of VKM's work through an up to date website

5. The Secretariat will make sure that short versions of risk assessments are made and published
6. The Secretariat will ensure that the established budget is followed
7. The Secretariat will make sure that administrative routines are followed
8. The Secretariat will strive for an effective and well functioning Secretariat in a good working environment